

Volumetric properties of some *n*-alkoxyethanols with alkyl acetates at the temperature 298.15 K

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The excess molar volumes V^E for binary liquid mixtures (*n*-alkoxyethanols + methyl acetate, ethyl acetate, propyl acetate) have been measured as a function of composition using a continuous dilution dilatometer at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure over the whole mole fraction range. The *n*-alkoxyethanols are ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, diethylene glycol monomethyl ether, triethylene glycol monomethyl ether, diethylene glycol monoethyl ether, and diethylene glycol monobutyl ether. The V^E for each of the mixtures are negative with the exception of propyl acetate + ethylene glycol monomethyl ether and change sign for methyl acetate + ethyl acetate + ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, or diethylene glycol monobutyl ether and ethyl acetate + ethylene glycol monomethyl ether. For each case, the V^E increases as the polar head group of the alkoxyethanol increases and decreases with increasing alkyl chain-length. The excess partial molar volume \bar{V}_i^E of the components are evaluated from the V^E results. The results are discussed on the basis of molecular interaction present in alkoxyethanol-alkyl acetate mixtures.

In continuation of our earlier studies on binary mixtures containing alkoxyethanol either with an organic solvent¹⁻³ or with water^{4,5}, we report here excess molar volumes of alkyl acetates with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, diethylene glycol monomethyl ether, triethylene glycol monomethyl ether, diethylene glycol monoethyl ether, and diethylene glycol monobutyl ether over the whole mole fraction range at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure. The aim of this work is to provide data for the characterization of the molecular interaction of these mixtures and to examine the effects of increasing the alkyl chain-length with a common polar head group, and of inserting oxyethylene groups with a common alkyl group in alkoxyethanol. An attempt is also made to compare the results by collecting the data on polyethers + ester mixtures. We also focus on the volumetric properties of an alkoxyethanol at infinite dilution in alkyl acetate.

Results and Discussion

The results of our measurements of excess molar volumes for all the binary mixtures at number of mole fraction at 298.15 K are graphically presented in Figs. 1-3. The values of V^E for all the systems are fitted to an empirical equation,

$$V^E = x_1 x_2 \sum_{i=1}^n a_i (x_1 - x_2)^{i-1} \quad (1)$$

where, a_i is the polynomial coefficients, n is the poly-

mial degree, and x_1 and x_2 are the mole fractions of the components 1 and 2, respectively. The values of the coefficients, a_i obtained by the least-squares method, with all points being given equal weightage, are presented in Table 1

Table 1. Values of the parameters of eq. (1) and standard deviations σ (V^E) for various binary mixtures

System	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	σ (V^E) $\times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$
CH ₃ COOCH ₃ +						
CH ₃ OCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	0.054	-0.167	-0.007	0.031		0.001
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.751	0.210	-0.085			0.003
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₃ OH	-1.298	0.417	-0.250			0.003
C ₂ H ₅ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.485	0.047	0.105	0.015		0.001
C ₄ H ₉ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.157	0.016	0.032	-0.158		0.001
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅ +						
CH ₃ OCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	0.030	-0.151	0.034			0.001
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.672	0.148	-0.065			0.002
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₃ OH	-1.125	0.116	-0.236			0.003
C ₂ H ₅ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.587	0.002	0.098	-0.132		0.001
C ₄ H ₉ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.553	0.015	0.070	0.087	-0.142	0.001
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇ +						
CH ₃ OCH ₂ CH ₂ OH	0.458	-0.165	0.020			0.002
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.419	-0.117	-0.044			0.001
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₃ OH	-0.933	0.216	0.186	-0.071		0.002
C ₂ H ₅ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.267	-0.111	0.024	-0.124		0.002
C ₄ H ₉ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH	-0.415	-0.001	0.091	-0.090		0.002

along with standard deviations σ . In each case, the optimum number of coefficients are ascertained from an examination of the variation of the standard deviation with n .

$$\sigma(V^E) = [(V_{\text{cal}}^E - V_{\text{obs}}^E)^2 / (n_{\text{obs}} - n)]^{1/2} \quad (2)$$

where, n_{obs} is the total number of direct experimental values. For all mixtures, $\sigma(V^E) \leq 0.003$ for the precision attainable with the dilatometer used.

Fig. 1. Excess molar volumes V^E at 298.15 K for the mixtures of $x_2\text{CH}_3\text{COOCH}_3$ + (O) $x_1\text{CH}_3\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$, + (Δ) $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$, + (□) $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$, + (×) $x_1\text{C}_2\text{H}_5(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$, + (●) $x_1\text{C}_4\text{H}_9(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$.

We have calculated excess partial molar volumes, $\bar{V}_1^E = (\bar{V}_1 - V_1^*)$ and $\bar{V}_2^E = (\bar{V}_2 - V_2^*)$ from V^E , where V_1^* and V_2^* represent the molar volume of the pure components. The partial molar volumes \bar{V}_1 and \bar{V}_2 in these mixtures are evaluated^{6,7} over the entire composition range by using eqs. (3) and (4),

$$\bar{V}_1 = V^E + V_2^* + (1 - x_1) (\delta V^E / \delta x_1)_{P,T} \quad (3)$$

$$\bar{V}_2 = V^E + V_1^* + (1 - x_2) (\delta V^E / \delta x_2)_{P,T} \quad (4)$$

The derivatives in eqs. (3) and (4) are obtained by differentiation of eq. (1). It leads to the following equation for the partial molar volumes of the alkoxyethanol (1) (\bar{V}_1) and of alkyl acetate (2) (\bar{V}_2),

$$\bar{V}_1 = V_1 + (1 - x_1)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n a_i (2x_1 - 1)^{i-1} + (1 - x_1)^2 x_1 \sum_{i=1}^n 2(i-1) a_i (2x_1 - 1)^{i-2} \quad (5)$$

$$\bar{V}_2 = V_2^* + (1 - x_2)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n a_i (1 - 2x_2)^{i-1} + x_2 (1 - x_2)^2 \sum_{i=1}^n (-2)(i-1) a_i (1 - 2x_2)^{i-2} \quad (6)$$

We are interested to focus on the partial molar volumes of

Fig. 2. Excess molar volumes V^E at 298.15 K for the mixtures of $x_2\text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_2\text{H}_5$ + (O) $x_1\text{CH}_3\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$, + (Δ) $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$, + (□) $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$, + (×) $x_1\text{C}_2\text{H}_5(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$, + (●) $x_1\text{C}_4\text{H}_9(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$.

Fig. 3. Excess molar volumes V^E at 298.15 K for the mixtures of $x_2\text{CH}_3\text{COOC}_3\text{H}_7$ + (O) $x_1\text{CH}_3\text{OCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{OH}$, + (Δ) $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$, + (□) $x_1\text{CH}_3(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_3\text{OH}$, + (×) $x_1\text{C}_2\text{H}_5(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$, + (●) $x_1\text{C}_4\text{H}_9(\text{OCH}_2\text{-CH}_2)_2\text{OH}$.

alkoxyethanol at infinite dilution ($x_1 = 0$) in alkyl acetate and the partial molar volume of alkyl acetate at infinite dilution ($x_2 = 0$) in alkoxyethanol. Therefore, we get from eq. (5) by putting $x_2 = 1$ (corresponding to $x_1 = 0$),

$$\bar{V}_1^0 = V_1^* + \sum_{i=1}^n a_i (-1)^{i-1} \quad (7)$$

Similarly, putting $x_2 = 0$ in eq. (6) we get

$$\bar{V}_2^0 = V_2^* + \sum_{i=1}^n a_i \quad (8)$$

In eqs. (7) and (8), \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 represent the partial molar volume of alkoxyethanol at infinite dilution in alkyl acetate and the partial molar volume of the alkyl acetate at infinite dilution in alkoxyethanol, respectively. Partial molar volume \bar{V}_1^0 at infinite dilution are listed in Tables 2 and 3. All of these partial molar volumes at infinite dilution are evaluated by using the Redlich-Kister coefficients (Table 1). Instead of using the Redlich-Kister coefficients, we have

Table 2. Partial molar volumes of alkoxyalkanol at infinite dilution in alkyl acetate at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure

System	$V_1^* \times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$\bar{V}_1^0 \times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (from eq. 7)	$V_{\phi,1}^* \times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (from eq. 12)	$\bar{V}_1^0 \times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (from eq. 14)
CH ₃ OCH ₂ CH ₂ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	79.25	79.43	79.52	79.54
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	79.25	79.46	79.55	79.56
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	79.25	79.93	79.93	79.98
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	118.21	117.32	117.10	117.06
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	118.21	117.33	117.30	117.11
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	118.21	117.86	117.87	117.85
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₃ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	157.43	155.46	155.42	155.20
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	157.43	155.96	155.98	156.18
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	157.43	156.54	156.50	156.49
C ₂ H ₅ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	136.37	135.93	135.93	135.93
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	136.37	136.01	136.00	136.19
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	136.37	136.36	136.33	136.34
C ₄ H ₉ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	171.15	171.14	171.13	171.33
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	171.15	170.42	170.45	170.34
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	171.15	170.91	170.88	171.88

also used another approach, which may be more convenient and accurate. This alternate approach makes use of the apparent molar volume that was originally defined by Lewis and Randall as

$$V_{\phi,1} = (V - x_2 V_2^*)/x_1 \quad (9)$$

and

$$V_{\phi,2} = (V - x_1 V_1^*)/x_2 \quad (10)$$

where, $V_{\phi,1}$ and $V_{\phi,2}$ are the apparent molar volumes of alkoxyethanol in alkyl acetate and of alkyl acetate in alkoxyethanol and V is the volume of a mixture containing one mole of (n -alkoxyethanol + alkyl acetate). It can be written as

$$V = V^E + x_1 V_1^* + x_2 V_2^* \quad (11)$$

Table 3. Partial molar volumes of alkyl acetate at infinite dilution in alkoxyalkanol at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure

System	$V_2^* \times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$	$\bar{V}_2^0 \times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (from eq. 8)	$V_{\phi,2}^* \times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (from eq. 13)	$\bar{V}_2^0 \times 10^6$ $\text{m}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$ (from eq. 14)
CH ₃ OCH ₂ CH ₂ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	79.81	79.72	79.70	79.68
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	98.50	98.41	98.36	98.66
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	115.61	115.89	115.87	115.87
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	79.81	79.35	79.21	79.06
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	98.50	97.91	97.88	97.75
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	115.61	115.03	115.06	115.25
CH ₃ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₃ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	79.81	78.69	78.73	78.72
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	98.50	97.25	97.28	97.28
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	115.61	115.02	114.97	114.96
C ₂ H ₅ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	79.81	79.49	79.49	79.48
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	98.50	97.88	97.86	97.87
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	115.61	115.14	115.19	115.16
C ₄ H ₉ (OCH ₂ CH ₂) ₂ OH +				
CH ₃ COOCH ₃	79.81	79.54	79.60	79.54
CH ₃ COOC ₂ H ₅	98.50	97.97	97.98	98.03
CH ₃ COOC ₃ H ₇	115.61	115.20	115.22	115.21

Combination of eqs. (11, 9) and (11, 10) leads to

$$V_{\phi,1} = V_1^* + (V^E/x_1) \quad (12)$$

and

$$V_{\phi,2} = V_2^* + (V^E/x_2) \quad (13)$$

Eqs. (12) and (13) permit easy calculation of the apparent molar volumes of each component from the experimental excess molar volumes and the corresponding mole fraction. Simple graphical extrapolation of $V_{\phi,1}$ to $x_1 = 0$ ($x_2 = 1$) and of $V_{\phi,2}$ to $x_2 = 0$ ($x_1 = 1$) gives values of $V_{\phi,1}^0$ and $V_{\phi,2}^0$ at infinite dilution. These are also the desired partial molar volumes at infinite dilution, represented by \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 same as before.

Perron *et al.*⁸ calculated partial molar volumes at infinite dilution from the excess molar volumes in another way as follows. This was obtained by rearrangement of eq. (13) and division by x_1 leads to

$$V^E/x_1x_2 = (V_{\phi,2} - V_2^*)/x_1 \quad (14)$$

Linear extrapolation of the 'reduced volume' represented by V^E/x_1x_2 to $x_2 = 0$ ($x_1 = 1$) leads to the desired \bar{V}_2^0 . In a similar way, linear extrapolation of the V^E/x_1x_2 to $x_1 = 1$ ($x_2 = 0$) leads to \bar{V}_1^0 . Thus linear extrapolation of V^E/x_1x_2 to $x_2 = 1$ or 0 is equivalent to our extrapolation of $V_{\phi,1}$ or $V_{\phi,2}$ to $x_2 = 1$ or 0 to obtain equally accurate values of partial molar volumes at infinite dilution, that is, \bar{V}_1^0 or \bar{V}_2^0 .

For all the mixtures studied, V^E is negative over the whole mole fraction range with the exception of propyl acetate with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether and change sign for methyl acetate with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether, diethylene glycol monobutyl ether and ethyl acetate with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether. For each ester, the V^E values become more negative with the addition of an OC_2H_4 group in the molecule of ethylene glycol monomethyl ether. This behavior is consistent with V^E for mixtures alkyl acetates with polyethers⁹⁻¹¹. Again, the magnitude of the excess molar volumes decreases with the size of the alkoxyethanols (i.e. with increasing the polar head group) in the sequence, propyl acetate > ethyl acetate > methyl acetate. The negative values of V^E suggests a strong chemical or specific interaction between the components which is maximum in the case of diethylene glycol monomethyl ether or triethylene glycol monomethyl ether-alkyl acetate.

For a given alkyl acetate, V^E is more negative for the alkoxyethanol with the lower alkyl chain. As for the shorter alkyl acetate (that is, with methyl acetate) V^E is lower, it must be due to interactional effects becoming more important and free volume effect decrease, particularly when the alkoxyethanol ends are of methyl character. Again, for larger alkoxyethanol when a large difference in size of the compounds exists, free volume effect becomes more important.

Partial molar volumes of alkoxyethanol at infinite dilution \bar{V}_1^0 in alkyl acetates are listed in Table 2. All of these \bar{V}_1^0 values of alkoxy ethanol in various alkyl acetate are smaller than the corresponding V_1^* values of pure alkoxyethanols except in mixtures of alkyl acetate with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether. This observation is consistent with the idea that the molar volume of alkoxyethanol is the result of the actual molecular volume plus the free volume that arises from the inter- and intramolecular self-association of pure alkoxyethanol molecules. This self-association become stronger either with increasing the polar head group or the alkyl chain ends of alkoxyethanols. One can picture the alkyl acetate molecules partially fitting into the open or empty spaces in liquid alkoxyethanol except for the ethylene glycol monomethyl ether-alkyl acetate system. This is true as the excess volumes for the mixtures of ethylene glycol monomethyl ether-alkyl acetate are mostly positive at lower x_1 .

We also note that all of the \bar{V}_2^* values for alkyl acetates in various alkoxyethanols (Table 3) are smaller than the

corresponding molar volume \bar{V}_2^* of the alkyl acetates except in mixture of propyl acetate with ethylene glycol monomethyl ether. One can say that the alkyl acetate molecules are partially fitting into the open or empty spaces in alkoxyalkanol molecules resulting in negative excess volumes.

We also observe that the partial molar volume of alkoxyethanol in alkyl acetate increases in the sequence, methyl acetate to propyl acetate. The difference between V_1^* and \bar{V}_1^0 values decreases with increasing size of alkyl acetate. Remarkably, the values of \bar{V}_1^0 for ethylene glycol monomethyl ether in alkyl acetate are larger than the corresponding values of V_1^* . This observation and also the negative V^E values obtained for other systems lead to suggest that the interaction between unlike molecules is more important than the structure-breaking effect between the like molecules. These interactions are relatively strong between diethylene glycol monomethyl ether or triethylene glycol monomethyl ether and methyl acetate, as suggested from V^E data. The positive values in the difference between \bar{V}_1^0 and V_1^* for ethylene glycol monomethyl ether-alkyl acetate can be attributed to the dispersion interactions, resulting in positive excess volumes. The methods of obtaining \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 by using eqs. (7) and (8), by extrapolating $V_{\phi,1}$ or $V_{\phi,2}$ values from eqs. (12) and (13) or by the equivalent extrapolation of V^E/x_1x_2 in eq. (14) as suggested by Perron *et al.*⁸ are all satisfactory and lead to similar results, as listed in Tables 2 and 3. The worst disagreement in the calculation of \bar{V}_1^0 and \bar{V}_2^0 in these three ways are within $\pm 0.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$.

Experimental

The diethylene glycol monobutyl ether (<98%, Fluka) was used as such. The origin and purities of other chemicals used have been described earlier^{1,12,13}. All liquids were stored in dark bottles over 4 Å molecular sieves. Before the measurements, all liquids were partially degassed under vacuum. The purity of the liquids was checked by measuring and comparing the density at $298.15 \pm 0.01 \text{ K}$ and atmospheric pressure with the corresponding literature values^{9,14-27} (Table 4). Density was measured with a bicapillary pycnometer that gave an accuracy of 5 parts in 10^5 . The composition of each mixture was obtained with an accuracy of one part in 10^{-4} from the measured apparent masses of the components. All the mass measurements were performed on an electronic balance (Dhona 200D, accuracy $\pm 0.1 \text{ mg}$). All apparent masses were correlated for buoyancy. All the molar quantities were based upon the relative mass table of 1985 issued by IUPAC²⁸.

Table 4. Observed and literature values of densities (ρ^*) for pure liquid components at 298.15 K and atmospheric pressure

Component	$\rho^* \times 10^{-3} / \text{kg m}^{-3}$	
	Obs.	Lit.
Ethylene glycol monomethyl ether	0.9602	0.96024 ^a 0.96020 ^b
Diethylene glycol monomethyl ether	1.0164	1.0167 ^a
Triethylene glycol monomethyl ether	1.0430	1.04310 ^c 1.04524 ^d
Diethylene glycol monoethyl ether	0.9839	0.9841 ^a 0.983589 ^e 0.98387 ^f
Diethylene glycol monobutyl ether	0.9479	0.948016 ^e 0.94808 ^g 0.94916 ^h
Methyl acetate	0.9282	0.9282 ⁱ 0.9279 ^j
Ethyl acetate	0.8945	0.89449 ^k 0.8948 ^l 0.89455 ^j 0.8948 ^l 0.8943 ^m
Propyl acetate	0.8834	0.88333 ⁿ 0.8831 ^p

^aRef. 14, ^bRef. 15, ^cRef. 16, ^dRef. 17, ^eRef. 18, ^fRef. 19, ^gRef. 20, ^hRef. 21, ⁱRef. 22, ^jRef. 23, ^kRef. 9, ^lRef. 24, ^mRef. 25, ⁿRef. 26, ^pRef. 27.

Excess molar volumes (reproducible to $\pm 0.003 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$) were measured directly with a continuous dilution dilatometer²⁹. Details of its calibration, experimental setup and operational procedures have been described previously^{30,31}. Each run covered just half of the mole fraction range, giving an overlap between two runs. A thermostatically controlled, well-stirred water-bath ($\pm 0.01 \text{ K}$) was used.

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